

Creating Guilt in Business

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ABSTRACT: This article describes the behavior of people involved in business relations, which seeks to meet individual needs as well as those of organizations. The need manifested through actions or inactions at individual or organizational level leads to enforcement of a guilty, capable of being sanctioned. If the guilt of the physical person is represented or guided by internal stimuli, so also the guilt of the organization or enterprise is represented by the satisfaction of the needs, of its needs, carried out legally or apparently legal by its organs. Unlike the typical entrepreneur's typology, the entrepreneur who adopts illicit business behavior plans, focuses, sets goals, allocates resources, creates products or services tailored to obtain the illicit outcome, observes as a rule the plan for increasing the number of victims, identifies new channels to attract potential victims, creates an apparent brand to capture and determine the victim to accept the illicit offer as an auction.

KEYWORDS: business, organization, guilty, entrepreneur, focus, business victim, apparent brand, need

Introduction

The social nature of human beings has determined that behavior has an adaptable significance in the realization of individual needs. Any human behavior has a certain meaning and depends on both the individual and the environment. The voluntary act of any person is related to his / her own motivations and pulsations, thus realizing the fundamentals of affectivity. The tendency to commit an act must fit into a certain behavioral structure that will withstand the socio-moral demands imposed by law (Daneş and Papadopol 1960, 267). The violation of the rules and general principles of human behavior determines the fair sanction of those who violate them and must ensure their social reformation. The way to react to a certain fact is determined by the possibility of adapting the individual to the situation.

Responsibility of the illicit entrepreneur - a sine qua non condition for the work done

Individual responsibility implies a personal commitment to accept the sanction of the authority for violating social or moral laws. Effect of lack of accountability, the punishment of the author intervenes for legal liability (criminal, civil, administrative) or for moral responsibility. The responsibility of the perpetrator of the act lies in the fact that there is a causal link between his act and his dangerous result.

Human activity is preceded by a psychic process that is objectively characterized by a concrete act. Human psychic activity is not a simple form of appreciation and response to natural and social stimuli, because before acting, the individual decides on the realization of a performance, which he leads and controls through the concrete form of manifestation (Bulai 1997, 155).

In the course of criminal activity, which will produce a socially dangerous result, there is an individual's concern for the regulation of behavior by anticipating the outcome in relation to the intended purpose and mobile action. The decision to commit a dangerous deed is always done for the perpetrator to achieve a conscious goal (Sutton and Rao 2014, 108).

The attitude of the individual is dependent on the environment, on social relationships and activity, adapting and reacting to environmental stimuli. Individual behavior also depends on sensory signaling, psychic acts that will determine the relationship between the individual, personality, and the environment. Disruption of brain processes generates annihilation or reduces individual mental processes that provide behavioral balance and individual orientation in relationships with other individuals (Sutton 2010, 168). There is a direct connection between the action and the person who commits it, in the sense that the result is assumed by the author and produces the consequences sought or not accepted by the author. The connection of man to the environment is accomplished through sensations, which are psychic phenomena resulting from the

stimulation of a receptor organ, thus obtaining the concrete attributes of objects and phenomena in the form of simple (simple) images.

Human activity is initiated and accomplished in a way that will ensure that it has a certain interest in adapting to the external environment. Closing or overcoming obstacles implies the existence of a decision and an active control to ensure behavioral stability. Deliberate actions prove the existence of the ability to represent the result in relation to the necessity of its production. The conscious and pursued goal of the individual corresponds to the motivational motivation, leads and controls the way the action is performed (Antoniou 1995, 78). From the multitude of purposes, the mentally chosen is the one who adapts to the concrete conditions. In performing any voluntary action, it also reflects the affective way of assessing its consequences, by mobilizing and concentrating the psycho-vigorous energy to reach the goal through the firm choice of decisions.

The phases of the illicit willful act of the businessman

In the realization of the voluntary act the individual behavior requires the following phases: the emergence of the action idea determined by the tendency, the need realized by a concrete situation. It imposes a certain tonality in meeting individual needs, causing feelings and passions on motivating needs and the intensity of this motivation. Behavior is motivated by internal changes (neuroendocrine) and external stimuli (medium) that act on the brain.

The confrontation of the action motives presupposes the rapid succession or the coexistence, under the influence of the external factors or the internal idea, of several reasons that move the human organism, until the acceptance of a reason and implicitly to the reduction of the motivational confrontation. But because any behavioral attitude is based on a number of conscious and unconscious, physiological, affective and social factors, they will be motivated by individual, moral or immoral behavior (Padovani 1990, 201).

The Voluntary Act provides active freedom but also determines social responsibility because conduct is determined by individual action motives. In the sphere of causality, any action requires individual responsibility, for the perpetrator has the possibility to do or not to act.

Adoption of the judgment explains the rational design of an action plan, the orientation towards a predetermined purpose, and the assessment of the individual capacity to achieve the goal by using, concentrating and directing all individual actions. The will of the individual will analyze and integrate processes and mental states in the voluntary activity assessed by reference to previous experience, by unifying affective energies and by suppressing trends contrary to the intended purpose. The decisional act also includes the personality traits of active temperament (Tănăsescu 2014b, 199), the desire to act, the fear of failure.

The intensity of the will is found in the significance given to the action and in the effort of accepting the main reason and in the decision to achieve the purpose of the action. The voluntary setting of the action involves direct, permanent and stable confrontation between the mental plan and the action plan.

Execution of the adopted decision consists in the effective realization of the action plan and concrete fulfillment of the proposed goal. Achieving the goal requires the use of specific material and mental means, the excessive desire to properly execute the mental plan as well as the modification and adaptation of the plan to the concrete conditions.

The individual performs simple actions immediately, with a low psychological effort, and complex actions require returns to improve the plan, a moment of preparation between judgment and execution, acquiring knowledge, improving skills, revolt against established rules. The lack of favorable conditions leads to the occurrence of the inhibition that offers the termination of the voluntary act, the postponement of the execution or the triggering of the voluntary act (Petricu and Voiculescu 1967, 334). The intensity of the effort of will is imposed by the individual experience, the concrete conditions, the character of the individual, the needs. Voluntary acts are aware of the individual being accompanied by vigilance and strong emotions in the execution of the act or are consciously determined by unconscious motivations.

At certain moments, the individual also proceeds to verify the result of the product in order to arrive at conclusions about how to achieve future facts at a high degree of appreciation by adopting methods and using specific means by forming new skills that will characterize the capacity of his or her voluntary effort.

The voluntary act exists and develops as a result of the individual's need to carry out countless actions to achieve certain results under different action circumstances.

Social conflicts are the source of imbalance and tension, of socio-individual confrontations both mentally and physically. Action-illicit omission (omission) causes social confrontations and requires the formation of social structures for interaction and sanction by society. The social approach to any illicit deeds has to be found in the interactive structure: the illicit act - the social reform punishment (Tănăsescu 2014a, 234).

The offense provokes a conflict between the perpetrator of the act of contesting the form, the content of the social relationship and the idea of the stability of the social relationship protected by a criminal norm. The conflict between the perpetrator of the illicit deed and the established legal norm and adopted precisely to ensure the exercise of the rights of other individuals determines two possibilities: the social reform of the individual by punishment or the reformation of the punishment system by removing obsolete obstruction rules, tightening or reducing the sanctioning role of punishment (Lăpăduși, Voinea 2015, 298). Legislative will enshrines the principles, rules, and rules that necessitate the recommendation of an abstract attitude or behavioral manifestation by participants in concrete social relations, as well as the legal consequences deriving from their willful violation.

The sanctioning of an illicit act is in line with social reality because it takes place in an interaction sphere: illicit deed - illicit punishment. The social experience of the perpetrator, the different inter-individual confrontations he has solved, determines an original sense in the mechanism of accepting or rejecting punishment.

The analysis and synthesis of the elements that make up the action as well as their comparison determines the awareness of the consequences that determine the inconsistencies or inconsistencies between the individual's appreciation mode, the level of consciousness, and the relationship established between the action of the consciousness committed and the representativeness of its consequences. Individual psychic activity is dominated by impulses, tendencies, instincts, innate spiritual qualities that form unconscious life, and the control exercised over them by conscious life (Padovani 1965, 187).

Conclusions

As a rule, an illicit entrepreneur creates, develops and adopts ideas that relate to a certain social value. It sets the principles, criteria for that value, and tries to force them to be known by as many people as possible. Depending on the status of the person who spreads the idea, it aims at developing, implementing it in different types of relationships. It models the implementation of the idea in such a way that it is adopted and respected by as many victims as possible. After checking in pilot projects, the idea is scaled globally, as well as in other areas, the idea becoming a standard in illicit.

Once the idea has been implemented to a certain standard in illicit business, illicit entrepreneurs focus and become aware of the activities they carry out, and after a certain period they enter into a habit that leads to a lack of control. If the application of the standard was creative and followed step by step, after the illicit business model scaled the creativity suffers, the focus on the implementation mode diminishes, the number of mistakes increases, and the illicit business man becomes negligent, anxious, and the relationships within the environment illicit or changing, the organization losing its trust in its leader.

As a paradox of trust, illicit organizations in criminal activity rely on trust, which must be secure, sincere among members of the group, in order to achieve the goal of harboring the trust of future victims.

In national societies, compliance with legislation generates values or non-values related to honesty, fairness to the defense of company or staff assets. Confidence in the standard, in the period

between implementation and habit, gradually decreases with the transformation of a volunteer slave (Tănăsescu 2018c) into a new leader, with new ideas, new methods, following a new stage of integration. As a rule, standards do not provide for a uniform sanction even from creation. Only after the breach of the standard begins, each illicit or implementing organization begins to establish a system of sanctions for various deviations and pay more attention to disregarding confidence.

States or organizations, when establishing trusted standards of trust, that entrepreneurs and individuals have to respect, from the outset, create, modify and apply the same sanction for the same type of offense. The uniformity of sanctions for disregarding trust at global level must be a common goal to create the same legal, economic, social framework, compared to the same standardized value, trust thus becoming a value of social relations, sanctioned the same in every state. Differences in the creation and enforcement of sanctions are those that allow an unacceptable elasticity of the standard, which remains thus obsolete.

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